

**Summary Report of Zoonoses, Food-Borne and Water-Borne
Diseases
in the Slovak Republic in 2018**

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1. *Salmonella* spp.

7,222 cases were reported in 2018, which represents a 19 % increase compared to 2017 and a 43 % incidence compared to the past five-year average. Cases were reported from each region of the Slovak Republic, while the highest morbidity was recorded in the regions of Banská Bystrica and Trnava. The lowest morbidity was recorded in the Košice region.

Fig. 1 Human Salmonellosis Incidence—Trend in the 20 Past Years (Morbidity green line, Trend – red line; Morbidity/100,000) Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR

Fig. 2 Salmonellosis Incidence according to District in 2018 (<0.00 – 0.02); <0.02 – 145.48); <145.48 – 218.22); <218.22 – 290.96); <290.96 – 363.70); <363.90 – 436.44>; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

Cases were recorded in every age group. Age-specific morbidity was highest among children from 1 to 4 years of age while the lowest morbidity was recorded last year among individuals from 35 to 44 years of age. The highest incidence of cases occurred in May, June and September. *S. Enteritidis* occurred most frequently in the disease aetiology (81.2 %) and carriage (78.2 %) just as in 2017. The following also occurred in the aetiology: *S. Typhimurium* in 3.5 %, *S. non specified* 2.5 % and *S. Infantis* in 2.1 % cases. Imported infections were in 3 cases as carriage and in 60 cases in the form of the actual disease. There were 560 outbreaks of salmonellosis. *S. Enteritidis* was the dominant etiological agent just as in the previous years. The most frequent factor of transmission was mixed food, home eggs and eggs in retail.

15,464 foods were examined in 2018. The percentage of positive samples in comparison with 2017 grew from 0.34 % to 1.24 %. Just as in the previous years, a higher percentage of positive samples was found in meat from broilers; in comparison with the previous year, a slight growth occurred from 6.3 % to 7.5 %. The most frequent serovars in food were again *S. Infantis* (43.7 %) and *S. Enteritidis* (40.6 %). Of 196 examined samples of eggs and egg products, 5.6 % were positive.

Among living animals, 5,475 flocks of poultry were examined, of which 1.6 % tested positive with *S. Infantis* and *S. Enteritidis* dominating. While in 2016, there were 2 recorded outbreaks of salmonellosis among poultry, in 2017 there were 8 outbreaks and in 2018 only one outbreak. *S. Infantis* dominated in other species of birds and *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Infantis* were most prominent among the other animal species.

384 fodder samples were examined in 2018, of which 1.6 % were positive.

The PHA SR, WMRI and SVFI examined 14,904 water and environment samples, of which 0.3 % were positive. Swabs from food establishments, the environment, eggs and sanitary tests were all negative. Water from wells, water supplies, water coolers, mineral water sources and pools were negative; in the case of surface water, 12 % of the samples tested positive. Of the 777 children's sandboxes that were tested, 6 samples showed salmonellosis. Rare isolates of *Salmonella* spp., which were the source of disease for several children and adult breeders, were isolated from water, swabs and the bedding litter of reptiles and tortoises.

The resistance of microorganisms to antimicrobial agents constitutes a real danger in treating infections. In 2018, the monitoring of the microbial resistance of isolates of *Salmonella* spp. acquired from the skins of slaughter broilers and turkeys for fattening and from the droppings of laying hens, broilers and turkeys for fattening was conducted. 115 isolates were obtained from the samples of carcasses of broilers, the most frequent was *S. Infantis* (64x) and *S. Enteritidis* (33x); no isolate was obtained from the samples of carcasses of turkeys.

82 isolates in total were obtained from the samples of droppings and the most frequent serovars were *S. Infantis*, *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium*. From the perspective of microbial resistance, the worst situation was found in the case of the isolates of *S. Infantis*, where the resistance varied from a slight degree of resistance to ampicillin, tetracyclines up to a high degree of resistance to quinolone and fluoroquinolone antimicrobial agents.

2. *Escherichia coli*

In 2018, in Slovakia there were 443 cases of disease caused by *E. coli*, and one case of STEC/VTEC and O26 serotype, and two smaller outbreaks. The offices of PHA SR and RPHA, SVFI and VFI, FChFT of SUT, WMRI and NCAF – FRI examined 52,700 samples of food, fodders, waters and environment in total.

The presence of *E. coli* was found in 4.3 % of the 8,244 food samples that were tested, and the presence of VTEC was confirmed in 8 out of 54 samples of raw meat. None of the feed samples tested positive to the presence of *E. coli*, but it was confirmed in 7.36 % of 20,036 samples of various water types. 6.42 % of 13,323 samples of drinking water failed to meet legislative requirements for quality and 8.03 % of 5,903 waters designed for recreational purposes failed to meet the relevant requirements. The presence of *E. coli* was examined in 24,415 samples from the environment and 3.75 % tested positive.

In terms of the resistance of *E. coli* to antibiotics under the harmonized monitoring of microbial resistance in herds or flocks of farm animals and their food commodities we have established 85 antibiotic profiles from 425 samples acquired from broiler holdings and from

150 broiler meat samples, 116 meat samples were positive to the presence of *E. coli* producing ESBL type enzymes, or AmpC. We also monitored the presence of overall and resistant strains of *E. coli* in 38 samples of waters, sediments and food.

3. *Yersinia* spp.

Yersiniosis-related morbidity from 2009 in Slovakia is higher than the average morbidity in the EU countries. 269 cases were reported in Slovakia in 2018, which is 22.8 % cases higher than in 2017.

Fig. 3 Incidence of Human Yersiniosis in the SR from 2007 (Morbidity/100,000; Year)

In 2018, the monitoring of *Yersinia* spp. in poultry meat was carried out. According to the conventional method of cultivation, 25 of 39 (64 %) samples of fresh chicken meat were contaminated by *Yersinia* spp. Based on the PCR confirmation method, 25.6 % (10/39) isolates were classified as *Yersinia enterocolitica*. In general, no presence of DNA specific for pathogenic bacteria *Yersinia enterocolitica* was detected, which in concert with bio-typing was based on phenotype; all isolates 26 % (10/39) were classified as 1A biotype, non-pathogenic biotype.

No *Y. enterocolitica* was recorded in 28 samples of droppings of dogs and zoo animals with enteritides, similar to the findings in the previous years.

4. *Cronobacter* spp.

No cases of human diseases were recorded in 2018. A total of 885 samples of first infant formula and follow-on formulas were specifically examined but the presence of *Cronobacter* spp. was not confirmed.

5. *Shigella* spp.

While the average morbidity rate in the EU/EFTA is around 1.4 per 100,000 individuals, in Slovakia the morbidity rate in 2018 was 3.8 per 100,000 individuals. Cases were reported in every age group and the highest age-specific morbidity was in children less than one year of age and children from 1 to 4 years of age. As in previous years, the highest morbidity was in the Prešov region where 12 outbreaks were recorded.

Fig. 4 Incidence of Dysentery according to District (<0.00 – 0.02; <0.02 – 22.21; <22.21 – 33.32; <33.32 – 44.43; <44.43 – 55.54; <55.54 – 66.64>; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

6. *Plesiomonas shigelloides*

Samples of surface water and the environment were not specifically examined for the presence of *Plesiomonas shigelloides* in 2018, as this agent was sporadically isolated from the waters when they were specifically examined for the presence of other microorganisms.

7. *Legionella* spp.

The incidence of diagnosed pneumonic forms of Legionnaire’s disease (LD) in Slovakia has a rising trend; in 2018 this infection was reported in 54 patients, which constitutes an incidence of 9.93 per million individuals, and which to date is the highest incidence of reported cases of LD in our country. The increase of the number of diagnosed cases is attributed to better cooperation with hospitals and clinics and the use of a highly sensitive test for the *Legionella* antigen in urine to identify infections caused especially by *Legionella pneumophila* 1 serogroup.

Fig. 5 Incidence of Legionnaire’s Disease per Million Individuals in the SR from 1985 to 2018 (blue - 1, 0, 0.4, 0, 0.2, 0.4, 1.1, 0.4, 0.6, 0.2, 0.6, 0.6, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 1.3, 1, 0.2, 0.2, 0.2, 1, 0.4, 1.7, 0.4, 0.6, 1.3, 0.8, 1.3, 2.6, 2.4, 2.58, 2.75, 9.93)

The infection particularly affected persons over 60 years of age with various risk factors. In the case of 4 patients, the *Legionella* infection could be deadly, but only in one case was

the sampling of water carried out in the household and tests showed the presence of *Legionella* as well as the infection of a mother in joint household.

Over 800 water samples in community conditions and up to 60 samples from healthcare facilities were tested for the presence of *Legionella* in the environment. The epidemiologically most significant *L. pneumophila* of 1 serological group, responsible for the most serious infections in the world, was present in almost 43 % of samples and the isolates of L.p. 3 serogroup were found in 49 % of the positive samples of waters verified by the PHA SR.

The analysis of the cases of Legionnaire's disease in our country showed the need to monitor the incidence of *Legionella* colonization in hydrotherapy facilities (spa, wellness); however, this requires amendments to the relevant legislation.

8. *Vibrio* spp.

As in previous years, no cases of cholera were reported in 2018. The identification of the incidence of various types of *Vibrio* in mineralized pool waters can be considered as significant. In 2018, a total of 122 *Vibrio* strains were isolated from 635 samples of pool and surface waters and swabs from pools; the most frequent was the *V. cholerae* non O1 non O139.

9. *Aeromonas* spp.

In 2018, a total of 153 strains of *Aeromonas* bacteria were isolated from tested waters with prevailing *A. hydrophila*.

10. *Campylobacter* spp.

In 2018, a total of 8,429 cases (morbidity 154.9 per 100,000) were reported in Slovakia, which represents a 19.4 % increase in comparison with 2017. The disease occurred in all regions, but as in the previous years the highest morbidity was in the Bratislava region – 235.1, and the lowest was in the Banská Bystrica region – 64.6.

Fig. 6 Incidence of Human Campylobacterioses in the SR from 1997 to 2018 (Green – morbidity, red – trend; Morbidity/100,000; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

The most frequently isolated bacteria with patients was *C. jejuni* and *C. coli*, and just as in the rest of the EU countries, *C. jejuni* was the most frequent cause of disease (87%).

Of 202 outbreaks, 5 were larger (3 and more persons), chicken meat was twice the factor of transmission, once it was contaminated hands, once contact with a sick person and twice the factor of transmission was unidentified. RPHA and SVFI laboratories tested 1,169 foods from mass caterers, food enterprises and the retail of which only 0.2 % tested were positive. Positive findings were confirmed only in 2 samples of fresh broiler meat.

Of the 1,473 of examined animals, 11.3 % were positive. The aforementioned data show that farm animals in particular are a reservoir of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. The prevalence has been around 1.7 % for several years; higher levels have been observed in pig farms – ca 19 %. a high level of *Campylobacter* spp. has been observed for a longer period of time in flocks of poultry; however, this is related to the active surveillance of this bacterial agent.

Higher resistance to tetracycline, ciprofloxacin and nalidixic acid in the case of isolates from animals shows a stable trend. Human isolates in Slovakia also show a higher level of resistance to ciprofloxacin and tetracycline, which correlates with the data from other EU Member States.

11. *Brucella* spp.

Brucellosis-related morbidity in Slovakia is lower than the average morbidity in the EU (0.09/100,000). Not a single case of brucellosis was reported in 2018. The SR is officially free of the incidence of bovine, ovine and caprine brucellosis. In order to maintain this status, 43,921 serological tests of cattle and 20,411 serological tests of sheep and goats were carried out in 2018.

12. *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*

9 cases of human granulocytic anaplasmosis (hga) were reported in 2018. 8 cases were reported in the Žilina region and 1 case in the Prešov region. The prevalence of *A. phagocytophilum* in ticks biting humans dropped from 9.6 % in 2017 to 5.0 % in 2018, with ticks biting animals – among Fallow deer (*Dama dama*) from the location of Pajštún near Bratislava, the prevalence was 71.4 %. In animals, the prevalence of *A. phagocytophilum* among Fallow deer was 20.6 % and 7.4 % among dogs

13. *Coxiella burnetii*

2 cases of human Q fever were reported in 2018; however, the antibodies indicating the disease were recorded in the serum of 4 patients from a sample of 51. A total of 2,197 samples of bovine animals, goats, sheep, wild hares and zoo animals were tested. Positive serological findings were found in only 2.31 % of cattle. *C. burnetii* was confirmed in one tick biting humans.

14. *Francisella tularensis*

The incidence of human tularemia in Slovakia has shown a decreasing trend since the outbreak in 2002; 6 cases were reported in 2018 (morbidity of 0.11/ 100,000), in comparison with 2017 with the lowest incidence, this represents a three-fold growth. The disease occurred in the Trnava, Nitra and Banská Bystrica regions.

Fig. 7 Incidence of Human Tularemia in the SR from 1990 to 2018 (Year; Morbidity per 100,000; 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5)

Ulceroglandular, pulmonary and non-specified forms of tularemia were diagnosed; the transfer was related to tick infestation and a contaminated environment with the incidence of small rodents.

1 focus of tularemia of hares was identified in 2018 in the Topoľčany district in the Nitra region. Of 48 samples of the European hares from approved hunts in 8 sites, one sample showed agglutination antibodies, with a 2.08 percent of positivity. Testing of 1,181 horses from 4 regions of Western Slovakia showed an overall seropositivity of 21.68 %. The surveillance results show the persistence of natural focuses of tularemia and the circulation of *F. tularensis* in the endemic area of Western Slovakia with the possibility of its further spreading and risk of infection.

Fig. 8 Incidence of Human Tularemia according to District in the SR in 2018, Incidence per 100,000 (0.00; 0.01 – 1.65; 7.61)

15. *Leptospira* spp.

Human leptospirosis in Slovakia shows a long-term decreasing tendency; however, the incidence of disease is probably significantly underestimated. One of the reasons for this may be the clinical course of infection – the course of certain parts of cases may be asymptomatic, or only with a slight clinical manifestation and are incorrectly diagnosed as a viral infectious disease or another disease. 2 individuals got sick in 2018. The serum of both patients reacted to the strains of the *Leptospira* serogroup *Pomona*.

Fig. 9 Human Leptospirosis Morbidity in the SR from 1949 to 2018 (Year; Per 100,000)

Of the 2,658 animals that were tested, 8.8 % were positive. The percentage of positivity grew in comparison with the previous years, particularly in cattle (from 4.6 % to 9.0 %) and in dogs (from 9.8 % to 13 %). Similar to the previous years, the dominant serovar among cattle was the *Leptospira* serovar *Sejroe*, while the dominant serovar among pigs was the serovar *Pomona*.

16. *Borrelia* spp.

981 cases of Lyme disease were reported in 2018, which is a 22 % increase in comparison with 2017 and 9 % higher than the 5-year average. The most cases were reported as Erythema chronicum migrans and a joint form of disease; a neurological form occurred in only 44 cases.

Fig. 10 Incidence of Human Lyme Disease in 2018 (green – Morbidity, red- Trend; Morbidity/100,000; Year; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

35 blood samples of dogs and 1 blood sample of sheep were tested serologically, where 22.9 % of the samples of dogs tested positive.

Fig. 11 Incidence of Human Lyme Disease according to District in the SR in 2018 (<0.00 – 0.02) <0.02 – 18.02) <18.02 – 36.73) <36.73 – 71.26) <71.26 – 106.71) <106.71 – 164.24>; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

Of the 324 ticks biting humans, 18.8% were infected by *B. burgdorferi* s. l., while in 2016 it was only 10.6 %. The prevalence of borrelioses in ticks from vegetation also significantly grew from 19.5 % in 2016 and 25.8 % in 2017 to 31.70 % in 2018. The highest prevalence (37.5 %) was in 2017 in the Furča urban forest in Košice, where in addition to the genospecies *B. garinii*, the genospecies *B. burgdorferi* s.s, which are less frequent, were significantly represented. Birds play a significant role in disseminating *B. garinii* in greater distances, as up to 34.0 % of ticks biting birds were infected by borreliae.

17. Chlamydiae

No cases of mammal chlamydiosis or Ornithosis (Psittacosis) in humans were reported in 2018. This was probably because differential diagnostics were not conducted and many infections were mistaken for a different diagnosis. 3,121 animal serums were tested for the presence of chlamydia antibodies, of which 5.99 % tested positive. Just as in the previous years, the highest seropositivity rate was detected in sheep (particularly after miscarriage or with reproduction disorders), and from 2015 positivity slightly dropped from 21.03 % to 17.23 % in 2018.

18. Mycobacterium spp.

281 cases of human tuberculosis were reported in 2018, which is an increase of 32 cases compared to 2017. As in the previous years, the highest morbidity was recorded in Eastern Slovakia. In terms of the health of animals, the SR continues to be free of incidence of bovine tuberculosis; in order to maintain this status, 42,737 tuberculin tests of cattle were carried out.

Fig. 12 Incidence of Human Tuberculosis in the SR and in the Surrounding Countries in 2018 (Austria 7.3; Hungary 8.0; Ukraine 76.7; Poland 17.0; Czech Republic 4.9; BA 4.46; TT 1.96; NR 2.95; TN 4.09; BB 2.31; ZA 5.06, KE 10.26; PO 7.89)

19. *Listeria* spp.

19 cases of Listeriosis and 4 deaths were reported in Slovakia in 2018. Most of the cases occurred among individuals between 55 and 64 years of age.

Fig. 13 Incidence of Human Listeriosis in the SR – Trend in Part Ten Years (green – Morbidity, red – Trend; Morbidity/100,000; Year; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

7,538 samples of 30 types of food were tested in 2018. The percentage of positive samples in comparison to 2017 dropped from 1.03 % to 0.81 %. A higher percentage of positive testing was found in raw sheep milk – 18.81 % and raw meat – 8.33 %. The percentage of positive testing among animals in 2018 grew from 6.51 % in 2017 to 8.05 % in 2018. In the case of animals, this particularly pertains to samples of brains, fetal membranes and abortions. 2,679 swabs were also tested for the presence of listeria, of which 0.04 % tested positive. Of all isolated strains, the most frequently isolated serotype was 1/2a, as in the previous years.

20. *Bacillus anthracis*

The last case of animal anthrax in the Slovak Republic was recorded in 2014 and the last case of human anthrax was recorded in 2003. Laboratory testing of animals is indicated only in suspect cases; in 2018, one animal sample was examined with a negative outcome. All 21 samples of raw material from the leather industry were tested with negative outcomes and none of 21 suspect samples revealed *B. anthracis* spores.

21. Clostridium spp.

In 2018, *Cl. botulinum* did not cause any disease in the SR. No cases of diarrhea caused by *Cl. perfringens* were reported. The number of infections caused by *Cl. difficile* grew by 29.9 % in comparison with 2017; 3,383 cases were reported. No epidemic incidence was recorded; however, 9 deaths were reported.

Of the 1,658 food samples that were tested for the presence of *Cl. perfringens*, only 3 samples of food from mass caterers were positive (0.18%). Of the 4,195 food samples tested for sulphite-reducing clostridia only 0.17 % were positive.

Of the 1,211 samples of clinically ill or fallen animals that were tested for clostridia, 49.55 % tested positive.

Of the 100 feed samples tested for *Clostridium* spp. only 2 % tested positive.

679 samples of drinking and mineral waters were also tested for the presence of *Cl. perfringens*; only drinking water tested positive (2.01 %).

22. Staphylococcus aureus (coagulase positive staphylococci and their toxins)

24 intestinal infections caused by *S. aureus* occurred in 2018, all within one outbreak.

12,195 food items were tested for the presence of CPS, of which 1.66 % tested positive. Most of the positive samples were in the “milk and dairy products” group. Staphylococci enterotoxin was detected in 5 food samples. The production of enterotoxin was proven in 21.25 % of isolates, most of them in delicatessen products.

The *S. aureus* was detected in 15.59 % of the 2,546 samples of clinically sick animals. The VFI DK did not confirm a resistance to ceftiofur in any of 178 isolates of *S. aureus* originating from animals, i.e. no MRSA isolates were detected.

The presence of coagulase positive staphylococci was confirmed in 1.52 % of the 32,412 water and environment samples. Methicillin resistant *S.aureus* were not detected at the RPHA in isolates of meat, water and from hospital environments; 3 isolates of *S. aureus* originated from the food industry environment, and milk and clinical material showed Methicillin resistance.

23. Enterococcus spp.

232 cases were reported in 2018; in the etiology of which *Enterococcus* spp. participated, the most frequently isolated was *E. faecalis* – 71.98 %.

47.7 % of 44 food samples tested positive, the highest percentage of positive samples – 87.5 % were non-pasteurized smoothies and cheeses from non-pasteurized sheep milk.

Of 19,194 water samples, 5.2 % were above the limit or positive.

Of 24,331 samples of the environment, 2.9 % showed the presence of the genus *Enterococcus* spp. bacteria; the most positive samples were surface water sediments. Enterococci resistant to antibiotics were present in the samples of sewage and surface water, surface water sediments and smoothies.

Resistance to ampicillin and gentamicin prevailed. In the case of 29 isolates from waters and sediments, 48 % were multi-resistant. Excessive production of bacterial efflux pumps was recorded in 76 % of isolates and the presence of the *vanA* gene was found in 33 % of enterococci isolates.

24. Lyssavirus

The last case of human rabies was recorded in Slovakia in 1990. Rabies in animals was diagnosed for the last time in 2015.

898 animals were tested in 2018, all tested negative. 632,800 vaccination doses for the oral vaccination of foxes were carried out as part of the eradication program.

25. Influenza Virus

216,504 cases of influenza and influenza like diseases (ILD) with a morbidity of 8,607.2/100,000 population were reported in 2018. Of the 39 cases of SARI, 13 cases resulted in death. In 589 cases, the influenza virus strains were isolated, which represents 83.4 % of the total number of positive samples. The B influenza virus prevailed markedly in samples positive to influenza in 2018 (471 cases), which represents 80 % of influenza viruses.

In 2018, the VI Zvolen serologically tested 1,960 blood samples from 115 poultry farming holdings without any positive outcome. 86 samples from wild birds and 38 samples from home farming poultry were tested by using the method for the detection of avian influenza. 4 samples from wild birds tested positive.

26. Tick-borne Encephalitis Virus

156 cases of Central European tick-borne encephalitis (morbidity of 2.87/100,000) were reported in 2018, which is twice as much as in 2017 and an increase of 27 % in comparison to the 5-year average. Similar to the previous years, the highest morbidity was in the Banská Bystrica region where 4 outbreaks were reported.

Fig. 14 Incidence of Human Tick-borne Encephalitis in the SR – Trend in 20 Years (green – Morbidity, red- Trend; Morbidity/100,000; Year; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

732 milk samples were tested with 4.5 % positivity in 2018. 364 herds were examined for the presence of the tick-borne encephalitis within the CS 391 targeted check-up, resulting in 0.82 % positivity. 32 pool samples of milk with 0% positivity were tested within own check-ups by the breeders and with the suspicion of the occurrence of the infection.

Within the CS 391 targeted check-up it was confirmed that pool samples of raw milk may serve for the identification of natural TBEV focuses. All-season monitoring of pool samples of milk were also carried out; this enabled the introduction of the method for determining the presence of the RNA (TBEV) virus when checking fresh cheese. The antibodies were tested in 388 serum samples of sheep and goats with 5.15 % positivity. 218 full vein uncoagulated blood samples of goats with no positive outcome were tested for the presence of RNA (TBEV) virus (RT PCR).

In 2018, the IoVi SAS examined 382 samples of ticks (in 71 pools) collected directly from the vegetation and the positivity was confirmed in 32 % of pools; 3 *Ixodes ricinus* nymph ticks biting on humans were also examined but the presence of a virus was not confirmed.

Fig. 15 Incidence of Human Tick-borne Encephalitis according to District in the SR in 2018 (<0.00 – 0.01); <0.01 – 3.20); <3.20 – 6.34); <6.34 – 9.85); <9.85 – 23.93>; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

27. West Nile Virus – WNV

In September 2018, one case was imported from Hungary diagnosed as A 92.3 West Nile Fever.

376 serum samples of horses and birds were tested for the presence of WNV antibodies in 2018, of which 1.32 % were positive. Specific antibodies were recorded in one horse (0.82 % of positive) and 4 birds (1.57 % of positive). Viral RNA was confirmed in the brains of three birds of prey, two Northern Goshawks and one Great Grey Owl, which died with clinical symptoms.

28. Dengue Virus

7 cases were recorded in 2018 (0.07/100 000), while in 2017 there were only 2 cases.

1 case was imported from Cambodia, contracted by a man between 25 and 34 years of age from the district of Malacky.

3 cases were imported from the Maldives, 3 persons from the district of Púchov contracted this virus (a child 1 to 4 years of age, a woman 20 to 24 years of age, and a man 30 to 34 years of age). Patients indicated in their epidemiologic history that they were bitten by mosquitos and did not use any repellents. The IgM posit., Subtype 1 of Dengue fever virus was confirmed by the ELISA test.

3 cases were imported from Thailand, 3 persons from the district of Bytča contracted the disease (a man 25 to 34 years of age, a woman 35 to 44 years of age, and a woman 25 to 34 years of age). Patients indicated in their epidemiologic history that they were repeatedly bitten by mosquitos. The IgM posit., Subtype 1 of Dengue fever virus was confirmed by the ELISA test.

29. Hantaan Virus

88 cases of hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome were reported in 2018; in comparison with 2017 it represents a growth of 1.7-times. Cases were reported from all regions, but up to 54 % of cases occurred in the Eastern Slovakia. In one case, the disease was imported from Malaysia.

30. Norwalk Virus

The number of reported virus-associated intestinal infections caused by NoV grew from 1,434 cases in 2017 to 2,798 cases in 2018. Up to 101 outbreaks were recorded, of which 29 were of a larger size. Two samples of small frozen berries were tested for the presence of NoV with a negative outcome.

Fig. 16 Incidence of Human Norovirus-associated Intestinal Infections according to District in the SR in 2018 (<0.00 – 0.02); <0.02 – 72.00); <72.00 – 107.99); <107.99 – 143.99); <143.99 – 179.99>;
Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

31. Rotavirus

4,012 cases of rotavirus intestinal infections were reported in Slovakia in 2018. 22 cases were imported, the most cases were from Croatia. No deaths were recorded. Rotaviruses in food and water were not examined in 2018.

Fig. 17 Incidence of Rotavirus Diarrhea Infections according to District in the SR in 2018 (<0.00 – 0.02); <0.02 – 83.77); <83.77 – 125.66); <125.66 – 167.54); <167.54 – 209.43); <209.43 – 251.32>;
Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

32. Hepatitis A Virus – HAV

In 2018 there were 173 cases of HAV in Slovakia (morbidity of 3.2/100,000), which represented a 74 % decrease in comparison with 2017. The highest morbidity was recorded in the regions of Banská Bystrica, Bratislava and Košice.

Fig. 18 Incidence of Acute Human HAV in the SR – 20-Year Trend (green – Morbidity, red – Trend; Morbidity/100,000; Year; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

High morbidity among children from 1 to 4 years of age and from 5 to 9 years of age again indicates that the recommended vaccination of 2-year-old children living in an environment with low hygienic standards is applied only rarely in certain regions and does not affect the morbidity. 21 cases were imported in 2018.

In 2018, 20 samples of frozen strawberries were taken in order to detect the presence of HAV. All of the samples tested negative for HAV.

Fig. 19 Incidence of Acute Human HAV in the SR according to District in the SR in 2018 (<0.00 – 0.02); <0.02 – 19.76); <19.76 – 29.65); <29.65 – 39.53); <39.53 – 49.41); <49.41 – 59.29>; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

33. Hepatitis E Virus – HEV

In 2018, 90 persons contracted HEV, which represents a 74 % growth in comparison with 2017. Just as in 2017, the most cases were in the regions of Banská Bystrica and Košice, but in 2018 it was also the Trnava region. 6 cases of infection were imported.

None of the food and water samples were tested for the presence of HEV in 2018.

In the case of animals, 589 samples of non-commercially kept pigs were examined. 15.8 % of samples tested positive.

Fig. 20 Incidence of Human HEV in the SR – 10-Year Trend (green – Morbidity, red- Trend; Morbidity/100,000; Year; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

Fig. 21 Incidence of Human HEV according to District in the SR in 2018 (<0.00 – 0.02); <0.02 – 5.16); <5.16 – 7.75); <7.75 – 10.33); <10.33 – 12.91); <12.91 – 15.49>; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

34. Prions

In 2018, the incidence of the CJD was confirmed in 18 cases, which represented a return to the incidence of CJD cases in 2015. The most cases were recorded in the regions of Žilina, Košice and Trenčín. The youngest patient with a genetic form of CJD was 45 years old.

7,961 samples from bovine animals were tested for BSE with negative outcome. 13,422 samples from sheep and goats were tested for scrapie, the positivity of sheep was 0.05 % (atypical form of scrapie), in case of goats no positive cases were recorded, similarly as in the previous years. Although the last recorded case of positive BSE in Slovakia was diagnosed in 2010, the incidence of scrapie in sheep population continues.

Fig. 22 Incidence of CJD Cases in Slovakia from 2010 to 2018 (Number of Cases)

35. *Toxoplasma gondii*

85 cases were reported in 2018 (morbidity of 1.56/100,000), which represents a 23 % decrease in comparison with 2017 and a 47 % decrease in comparison with the 5-year average. The congenital form of toxoplasmosis (P37.1) was not recorded.

Fig. 23 Incidence of Human Toxoplasmosis in the SR –20-Year Trend (green – Morbidity, red – Trend; Morbidity/100,000; Year; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

Fig. 24 Incidence of Human Toxoplasmosis according to the Districts in the SR in 2018 (<0.00 – 0.01); <0.01 – 5.07); <5.07 – 7.60); <7.60 – 10.13); <10.13 – 12.67); <12.67 – 15.20>; Source: EPIS, Public Health Authority of the SR)

260 samples of meat juices from various types of meat of Slovak origin were examined from October 2016 to March 2018 for the presence of specific *T. gondii* antibodies, of which 23.08 % were positive. There were no positive findings in beef; the highest number of positive cases occurred with sheep, goat and wild boar meat (71 %, 50 % and 39 % respectively). 12.9 % of the pork samples tested positive and there was a marked difference between pork from large commercial farms, where positivity was 8.1 % and pork from small farms, where positivity was as high as 41.2 %.

In 2018, the SVFI examined 769 samples of droppings of cats, Felidae carnivores and animal blood. Positive findings were at the level of 3.3 % of all examined samples. Of the 662 samples of droppings of cats and Felidae, one sample was positive. Of the 107 animal blood samples, 22.4 % were positive, while in 2017 it was 35.4 %. Of all species of animals, dog blood showed the highest percentage of positivity, up to 84.6 %. In comparison with 2017, we also recorded the growth of positive samples with bovine animals from 15.4 % to 40.0 %. All cat blood samples were negative and only one sample of cat droppings was positive.

36. Plasmodium spp.

5 imported malaria cases were reported 2016, while in 2017 we recorded only 1 case of a man who contracted malaria after being in a jungle in Liberia; in 2018 we recorded 3 cases of imported malaria.

37. Babesia spp.

674 dog blood samples were tested from 2002 to 2018 with a positive outcome for *Babesia* spp. in 163 samples. The majority of tested samples originated from dogs suspected of babesiosis and thus it did not represent survey of independent dog selection. The resulting percentage of 26.18 % therefore cannot be considered to be an indicator of the prevalence of this parasite among dogs in Slovakia. In 2018, *Babesia* spp. was tested and proved by PCR method also in the blood of a calf from the district of Trnava. The greatest share of positive findings comprised samples from dogs which resided or had access to the regions of the Danube and Morava river basins, while dogs from the surroundings of Košice also comprised a high share of positive cases. The number of positive cases from the regions of river basins and their surroundings prove the link of the parasite to the hygrophilous type of vector of the tick *Dermacentor reticulatus*. However, owners who stated that their dogs live only in urban environments also tested positive.

38. Echinococcus spp.

10 cases were reported (morbidity of 0.18/100,000) in 2018, which is 3 cases more than in 2017. The disease was contracted by patients in the regions of Banská Bystrica – 5 cases, and Prešov – 3 cases respectively, and one each in the Trenčín and Žilina regions. In 2018, the IoPa of the Slovak Academy of Sciences confirmed alveolar echinococcosis, diseases caused by the tapeworm *Echinococcus multilocularis*, with 3 patients from the Prešov region and 1 patient from the Banská Bystrica region.

145 foxes were examined for the presence of echinococci in 2018. The percentage of positivity in comparison with the previous year, when it markedly dropped to 10.66 %, grew again to 26.90 %. This growth is to a large extent affected by the marked drop in the number of tested samples from less infested regions. We consider the current conditions of echinococcosis monitoring – testing of foxes in specified areas of Slovakia affected by oral vaccination (regions of Žilina and Prešov), insufficient from the aspect of detection rate and prognosis of the further spread of *Echinococcus multilocularis*. This is because it is highly

probable that the number of infection focuses is much higher and includes areas of Slovakia, which will not be examined within the monitoring in the future. In comparison with the Czech Republic, where in 2018 they examined 2,905 foxes (709 positive cases), 145 Slovak foxes are only a symbolic monitoring of this infection. And in the past years we recorded new detections of *E. multilocularis* in foxes specifically in the regions of Southwestern Slovakia.

The reported positive findings of *E. granulosus* from slaughterhouses with animals examined only by inspection, without microscopic proof and ironically almost no laboratory detection of this kind with Canidae definitive hosts indicates the possibility of falsely positive outcomes. In 2018, from the total number of 2,501 tested dogs, only 3 dogs tested positive for the presence of echinococci eggs, from the regions of Košice and Košice vicinity. However, even with these dogs it was not an infection of *E. granulosus*; the testing of these findings by the PCR method identified the species as *Echinococcus multilocularis*.

39. *Taenia* spp.

While in 2016 taeniasis was not reported and in 2017 only one adult man contracted this disease (morb. of 0.02/100,000) in the Trnava region (dg. B 68.9 Non-specified Taeniasis), in 2018, two cases were reported (0.04/100,000).

Finding cysticercuses at slaughterhouses with pigs and bovine animals is relatively rare. While in the previous years the findings of cysticercoses with bovine animals or pigs were relatively rare, in 2018 no such case was reported.

40. *Toxocara* spp.

32 cases were reported in 2018, which is 13 cases less than in 2017. The largest number of cases have occurred in the Nitra region in the past 9 years. The most frequent manner of transfer is contact with a domestic pet/animal and via ingestion.

In 2018, a total of 125 persons were tested for the presence of antibodies against *Toxocara* spp. with suspect larval toxocariasis at the IoPa of the Slovak Academy of Sciences. Antibodies were detected in one case.

In 2018, a total of 3,246 samples of droppings and the intestinal content of definitive hosts of roundworms of genus *Toxocara* and *Toxascaris* were tested. 320 samples (9.86 %) tested positive for the presence of roundworms and their eggs, which is a slight increase in comparison with record-setting low prevalence in the previous year (8.60 %). a slight growth in positivity was reported, particularly among dogs (from 7.34 % to 9.48 %), but the percentage of positivity grew in comparison with the previous year also with cats and other types of animals.

41. *Trichinella* spp.

No human infections were reported in course of 2018 when the IoPa of the SAS examined 118 serum samples of patients for the presence of trichinellosis. The presence of antibodies against *Trichinella* spp. was confirmed in 4 cases (3.4 %).

667,161 animals were tested for the presence of *Trichinella* spp., with a positive testing of larvae in 14 samples. In comparison with 2017, when the prevalence of trichinellosis among foxes dropped to a record-setting level of 2.8 %, the prevalence grew again in 2018 to the level similar to the previous years of 2012 – 2016, when it varied from 8 to 11 %. From 2009 there were no positive cases reported among farm animals and positive cases are reported only among wild animals, foxes in particular (64.3 % of all positive samples in 2018).

Dominant type in Slovakia is *Trichinella britovi*, but in 2017 we also recorded one case of *Trichinella pseudospiralis* in a wild hog.

Fig. 25 Prevalence of *Trichinella* spp. among Foxes in the SR from 2009 to 2018 (vertically: 0.00%, 5.00%; 10.00%; 15.00%; 20.00%; 25.00%; horizontally: 6.74%; 9.95%; 20.43%; 9.70%; 10.61%; 7.66%; 8.46%; 10.50%; 2.84%; 8.04%)

42. *Anisakis* spp.

In 2018, just as in the previous years, no cases of human disease caused by roundworms *Anisakis simplex* were recorded.

51 samples of fish and salt water fish products were tested in 2018 for the presence of larvae of the *Anisakidae* family. Dead *Anisakidae* larvae were found in one sample of frozen herring fillets and in one sample of cod liver.

43. *Thelazia* spp.

The first cases of eye thelaziasis caused by the parasitic nematode *Thelazia callipaeda* were confirmed in the territory of Slovakia in 2016 and 2017. By the end of 2018, in total of 938 suspect or potential hosts were examined (dogs, cats, foxes, badgers, bears, racoons), and the presence of the parasite was diagnosed only in dogs, red foxes and in one cat. While up to 2017 only 16 positive cases of dogs and foxes were reported, in 2018 another 38 positive cases of thelaziasis with animals were reported (31 dogs, 6 foxes, 1 cat). The majority of cases occurred in the Bratislava and Košice regions.

To date, no human cases of this infection were recorded in Slovakia.

44. *Dirofilaria* spp.

In 2018, dirofilariasis was confirmed among humans by the IoPa SAS by analysing materials from histological slices and intestines acquired during the surgical extirpation of a subcutaneous knot by molecular methods in the case of 3 patients from the southern district of Slovakia.

Dog blood samples have been tested for the presence of dirofilariasis since 2005. The highest number of tested samples (367) was recorded in 2018 and the highest number of districts was included in the monitoring (16), where the prevalence of the infection was 9.26%. This is a significant indicator of infestation of Slovakia by these parasites for the future.

Dirofilaria repens causing the subcutaneous or eye form of disease is the dominant type in our territory. *D. repens* is also the cause of all heretofore diagnosed cases of human dirofilariasis in Slovakia.

45. Newly occurring risks – Ciguatoxin/Ciguatera

Ciguatera is the most frequent poison caused by the consumption of saltwater fish which are contaminated by so called ciguatoxin. Ciguatoxin is produced by the seaweed *Gambierdiscus toxicus*, which is found at coral reefs in tropical and subtropical waters. Herbivorous fish feed on this seaweed which are then food for larger carnivorous fish. Thus, the toxin appears in them in much more concentrated form than in the previous link of this food chain. Ciguatoxin may occur in more than 400 kinds of saltwater fish with a coral reef habitat. The fish with the highest risk for humans are barracuda, grouper, conger eel, jack mackerel, European bass and sturgeon. The increased number of poisonings in Europe in the past years is attributed to more intensive tourism, increased import of saltwater fish, as well as climate change and due to the adverse effects of human activity on coral reef ecosystems.

List of Acronyms

AHAW	– Animal Health and Welfare Network of EFSA
BMC	– bio-medicinal center
BSE	– bovine spongiform encephalopathy
CJD	– Creutzfeldt-Jacob Disease
WTP	– wastewater treatment plant
DNA	– deoxyribonucleic acid
ECDC	– European Center for Disease Control
EEA	– European Economic Area
EFSA	– European Food Safety Authority
EFTA	– European Free Trade Association
EREN	– Emerging Risks Exchange Network of
EU	– European Union
FChFT	– Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology
HAV	– Hepatis A virus
HEV	– Hepatis E virus
HUS	– hemolytic uremic syndrome
ILD	– influenza-like disease
ISBN	– International Standard Book Number
LFUK	– Faculty of Medicine of Comenius University in Bratislava
CPS	– coagulase positive staphylococci
LD	– Legionnaire’s diseases
MRA	– EFTA Network on Microbiological Risk Assessment
NCP	– National Contact Point for Scientific and Technical Cooperation with EFSA
NoV	– Norwalk virus
NRC	– national referential center
NAFC	- National Agricultural and Food Center
NICHD	– National Institute of Children’s Diseases Bratislava
IoPa SAS	– Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
RPHA	– Regional Public Health Authority
SARI	– Severe Acute Respiratory Infection
SAS	– Slovak Academy of Sciences
TL	– test laboratory
s.l.	– <i>Borrelia burgdorferi sensu lato</i> complex
SUT	– Slovak University of Technology
SVFI	– State Veterinary and Food Institute
TBC	– tuberculosis
TBEV	– tick-born encephalitis virus
IoE	– Institute of Epidemiology
TSE	– transmissible spongiform encephalopathies
DHW	– domestic hot water
CCTIA	– Central Control and Testing Institute in Agriculture
UVMPH	– University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy
PHA SR	– Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic
IoA SAS	– Institute of Zoology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
IoVi SAS	– Institute of Virology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
VFI	– Veterinary and Food Institute
VI	– Veterinary Institute
VTEC/STEC	– <i>E.coli</i> producing verotoxin/Shiga toxin
FRI	– Food Research Institute
WMRI	– Water Management Research Institute
WHO	– World Health Organization

WNV

– West Nile Virus